

A NOVEL PATCH ANTENNA FOR GPS APPLICATION

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Summary – Global Positioning System (GPS) technology has become an essential component in various applications, ranging from navigation to geolocation services. To meet the increasing demand for precision and reliability in GPS systems, antenna designs must evolve to enhance performance and adapt to diverse operating environments. Patch antennas, known for their compact size, low profile, and ease of integration, are widely utilized in GPS applications. In this study, a novel patch antenna design for GPS applications operating at 1.27 GHz and 1.46 GHz is proposed. The design process was conducted using Qucs Studio. The goal of this work was to achieve a compact and efficient antenna capable of providing high gain, stable radiation patterns, and minimal signal distortion at the targeted frequencies. The simulation results demonstrated favorable performance, meeting the design objectives for both frequency bands.

Key-words: Microstrip Line, Qucs, Patch, GPS, Electromagnetism.

INTRODUCTION

An antenna is the transitional structure between free-space and a guiding device [1], it's use to send or receive an electromagnetic wave, this means that an antenna is only supposed to send it's signal when the match frequency which was designed to work with, in this case 1.27 GHz and 1.46 GHz. A Microstrip Line antenna consist of a metallic patch on a grounded substrate.

A Microstrip Line is an antenna with a low profile build, which means that it can be mounted in a flat surface, it is simple and inexpensive to build. The main use of this type of antenna is wireless communication such WiFi, or in the case of this cited in the project, GPS applications, that is because, there is some types of GPS, the two that are covered by this antenna are the L1 band that uses around 1.57GHz, and the L2 band that uses around 1.22GHz [2].

Other differences between the two types of GPS bands are they use, the L1 band has better use for Civilians GPS applications, that's because it has a good accuracy but do not need much more power, while the L2 band has a better and more efficient accuracy, being better for the military signals and some types of civilians that need a more accurate location, which can be analyzed in Figure 1

Figure 1 – Two different types of gps bands

DEVELOPMENT

To start projecting the antenna, the software SciLab was used, we can use the code provided by

Alexandre Maniçoba in the SCILAB introduction and approach work, published in MAXLAB [3].

Now, with the antenna projected, by giving the measures and parameters, the program delivers the exact dimensions of the antenna, in width and length, including the substrate size and excesses necessary to work, that we call Delta L. The Height of the substrate is provided by the project, in this case is 1.6mm. The results can be checked in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – SciLab patch antenna calculator project.

Now, the measures provided by SciLab are used to design the same antenna in QucsStudio with the purpose of simulating and finding the results of his signals, opening QucsStudio, we can start a new project and begin configuring the substrate and

simulation parameters to the same used in SciLab, to do this we use the “S-PARAMETER” and “SUBST1” components, like in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Parameters set inside QucsStudio.

After the parameter are set, the actual antenna project can be made, to do this are used the “MICRO STRIP” components, that are in Transmission Lines category.

If we use the Provided dimensions provided by SciLab, we would end with an antenna that only can achieve 1.27GHz, witch is good, but not the result that we are seeking, to end up with a dual band antenna, we net to add new flanges to the antenna, so the antenna could receive and emit more than one type of wave frequency efficiently, and by that, we can project the antenna like in Figure 5, for the schematic, and in Figure 6, for the design.

Figure 5 – Dual band patch antenna assembly

After the build in QucsStudio, the dimensions are imputed in the W and L parameters in each component, after that, the simulation can be made, to do this, the F2 key can be pressed, after the simulations some values are shown, those are the results of the antenna in the pure theoretical and ideal application, but in the real world there are a bunch of things that will influence the results, to account these variables that can influence, we simulate the layout, to do so, we can press SHIFT + F10, or go to TOOLS in the top bar, then CREATE SIMULATION LAYOUT, after that, the simulation is run again, but this time, the results shown are the expected real life results.

Figure 6 – Simulated Layout in QucsStudio.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

After both simulations, the layout and the ideal, we achieve two different results, those who are shown next:

Figure 7 – Ideal Theoretical results

Figure 8 – Real life expected results

Analyzing the results, we can conclude that both had reached two different frequencies, but, we can also see that in the Theoretical results, the attenuation and power of the signal is really high, being above the expected limit of -10dB, that means that the antenna will not operate efficiently and can malfunction, by the other hand, the second simulation, the one with the layout and real life influences being taken into account, the results are far more better and expected, being still two different frequencies, but, in this time, with the both being below the -10dB mark, witch are the expected and ideal form of patch antenna [4].

With now the both frequencies being known, their use can be found, in that case, 1.27GHz and 1.46GHz are two of GPS bands, witch means that it can be used in L1 and L2 GPS band applications.

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